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RELATION BETWEEN EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE AND JOB STRESS AMONG ENGINEERS AT PUBLIC SECTOR

M.LAKSHMI, Assistant Professor in the Dept of Business Administration,
Krishnasamy College of Science, Arts and Management for Women, Cuddalore

Dr.G. SUGANTHI, Research Supervisor and Assistant Professor, Dept of Business Administration,
Thiru Kolanjiyappar Govt. Arts College, Viruthachalam

ABSTRACT

This present study aimed at exploring the relation between emotional intelligence and job stress. Emotional intelligence is an important trait for handling stress at work place. It was hypothesized that there will be significant influence of emotional intelligence on stress level among engineers. Data was collected from a sample of N=30 from engineers working a public sector organization at managerial level at Andhra Pradesh. Emotional intelligence was measured by a scale developed by M.K. Mandal, and job stress was measured using Occupational role stress scale by Uday Pareekh (1983). The mean and SD values were calculated and found to be moderate in case of stress level and higher in case emotional intelligence level. Regression analysis showed that influence of emotional intelligence was significant in occupational stress level among engineers at managerial level.

Introduction

All learning has an emotional base." – Plato. Our each and every action is controlled by emotions, this is the essential premise of Emotional Intelligence (EI). To be successful requires effective awareness, control and management of one's own emotions and those of others. EI has two aspects of intelligence: - Understanding yourself, your goals, responses, behavior, create possibilities and intentions.

Understanding others and their feelings

Emotional Intelligence (EI) refers to the ability to perceive, control, and evaluate emotions. Some researchers suggest that emotional intelligence can be learned and strengthened, while other claim it is an inborn characteristic. Researchers have argued that emotions are essential to rational thinking (Damasio, 1994) because they are tied to values. Although the upsurge in emotional intelligence construct started with Goleman in 1995 (Goleman, 1995). Since 1990, Peter Salovey and John D. Mayer have been the leading researchers on emotional intelligence. In their influential article "Emotional Intelligence," they defined emotional intelligence as, "the subset of social intelligence that involves the ability to monitor one's own and others' feelings and emotions, to discriminate among them and to use this information to guide one's thinking and actions" (1990). Salovey and Mayer proposed a model that identified four different factors of emotional intelligence: the perception of emotion, the ability reason using emotions, the ability to understand emotion, and the ability to manage emotions.

Two theoretical paradigms are available on emotional intelligence: ability and mixed model. Ability

models regard emotional intelligence as a pure form of mental ability and thus as a pure intelligence. In contrast, mixed models of emotional intelligence combine mental ability with personality characteristics such as optimism and well-being (Mayer, 1999). Mayer & Salovey's model falls under ability model category while Goleman and Reuven Bar-On represent the mixed model of EI. On a global level, all of the models aim to understand and measure the elements involved in the recognition and regulation of one's own emotions and the emotions of others. Ciarrochi et al. (2000) also suggested that there may be consensus across models in terms of four important shared areas: emotion perception, regulation, understanding and utilization.

Emotional Intelligence Quotient (EQ) is increasingly relevant to organizational development and developing people, because EQ principles provide a new way to understand and assess people's behaviors, management styles, attitudes, interpersonal skills, and potential. Emotional Intelligence Quotient is an important consideration in all aspects of an organization: human resources planning, job profiling, recruitment interviewing and selection, management development, customer relations and customer service, etc. Also EQ skills can be developed and improved over time.

The modern world, which is said to be a world of achievements, competition, is also a world of stress. One finds stress is everywhere whether within family, job, organization and in society. It is not surprising that interest in this issues has been rising with the advancement of the present century which has been called the "Age of anxiety or stress". Stress is involved in an environmental situation that

perceived as presenting demand.

Literature review

Which threatens to exceed the person's capabilities and resources for meeting it, under conditions where he or she expects a substantial differential in the rewards and costs from meeting the demand versus not meeting it (Mc Grath, 1976)? Work life is concerned extreme stress is so aversive to employees that they will try to avoid it by withdrawing either psychologically (through disinterest or lack of involvement in the job etc.), physically (frequent late coming, absenteeism, lethargy etc.) or by leaving the job entirely (Beehr and Newman, 1978). It predisposes the individual to develop several psychosomatic illnesses; in contrast, the absence of extreme stress would result in more satisfied, happy, healthy and effective employees.

However, the stress one experiences in the job vary from mild to severe depending one's physiological, psychological and social make up (French and Caplan, 1970, Margolis et al., 1974., Miller, 1960 and Wardwell et al., 1964). It is also reported by many researchers that the low job satisfaction was associated with high stress (Hollingworth et al.1988, Abdul Halim, 1981; Keller et al., 1975; Leigh et al, 1988).Orpen (1991). It observed that major source of stress is derived from the occupational environment; role holders in certain occupation, irrespective of individual differences, are much more likely to experience stress.

Here, the emphasis is on the individual demands of various jobs that have the capacity over a period of time to exhaust the physical and psychological resource of employees in the job. Manshor, Fontaine and Chong Siong Choy (2003 organization) in their study examined the sources of occupational stress among Malaysian managers working in multi-national companies (MNCs).It was found that workloads, working conditions, and relationship at work were the main concern of the managers that lead to stress at the work place. The results also indicated that certain demographic variables do influence the level of stress among managers.Occupational stress is an increasingly important occupational health problem and a significant cause of economic loss. Occupational stress may produce both overt psychological and physiological disabilities.

However it may also cause subtle manifestation of morbidity that can affect personal well-being and productivity (Quick, Murphy, Hurrell and Orman, 1992). A job stressed individual is likely to have greater job dissatisfaction, increased absenteeism, increased frequency of drinking and smoking, increase in negative psychological symptoms and reduced aspirations and self-esteem (Jick and Payne, 1980 cited in Jayashree, 2000).

The context of the study The present study is an attempt to investigate emotional intelligence and how it influence in dealing with job stress and to compare the level of stress experienced by the engineers at managerial level. At

managerial level employees have to carry out multiple duties which may cause conflict and stress at work place. The study will be helpful to drawn up further policy on the related fields and act as a secondary data for further research

Method

Objective of the study

1. To study the occupational stress level among engineers at managerial level in public sector.
2. To study emotional intelligence level among engineers at managerial level in public sector
3. To study the influence of emotional intelligence on occupational stress level among engineers at managerial level in public sector.

Participants - For the present study, sample was collected from 30 engineers (Mean age=30 years) at Managerial level at a state run public sector power organization. Data was collected by using purposive random sampling technique.

Design of the study - It is a correlational study. The study aims to see the influence of emotional intelligence on occupational stress

Materials and Procedure - Emotional Intelligence scale: It was developed by **Manash K. Mandal**. It contains 40 items and five point scoring pattern from 1-5. Some items are reversed scored. This scale was found to have good reliability and validity in Indian population.

Occupational role stress scale by **Uday Pareekh (1983)**. It has 40 items and five point scale. The score for each role stress range from 0 to 20 and total score ranges from 0 to 200. The reliability of the test with each role stress dimension ranges from 0.45 to 0.73. It showed a good validity by the measure of self-consistency scale. The result showed a high internal consistency.

Procedure- The study was conducted on engineers at managerial level at public sector organization. The consent was taken from the participants and authority for the data collection. The questionnaires were distributed in office setting and asked the participants to fill it according to the instructions given. Data were collected by the investigator herself.

Discussion - The present study was carried out to find the influence of emotional intelligence on occupational stress level among employees at managerial level in public sector. Regression analysis was carried out and the result was placed in the following Table 1 and Table 2 respectively

Table No.-1 Showing Mean and Standard Deviation Values of Emotional Intelligence and Job Stress

Particulars	Mean	Std. Deviation	Correlation Co-efficient	N
Occupational Stress Index	96.67	6.604	.53	30
Emotional Intelligence	127.43	7.094		30

**Significant at .01 level of significance

It was indicated by results in Table 1 that mean stress level is average among engineers at public sector organization. Also emotional intelligence was found to be moderate level among the engineers at managerial level at public sector organization. Result in Table 1 also indicated that there is a positive strong correlation between emotional intelligence and occupational stress

Table 2 Showing Regression analysis between Emotional intelligence and Job stress

R	R square	Adjusted R	Standard error	F value	Sig
.532	.283	.257	5.692	11.036	.002

Above Table 2 showed the values of regression analysis and it was found that R value is .532. The R square values was .283 which means that there was around 28 percent influence on occupational stress was predicted by emotional intelligence. The F values found to be significant at .05 level of significance. So it can be interpreted that emotional intelligence significantly influenced the occupational stress level among engineers at managerial level in public sector organization.

Stress does not have same effect on all persons. Individual differences play important role in dealing with stressful situation. Some people go into pieces at the slightest provocation, while others deal effectively. Therefore emotional intelligence plays important role in dealing with stress in different situation. At managerial level communication ability is very important. Good communication ability means how a person expresses his emotion, can understand others, and also manage his emotion according to situation. Person with low emotional intelligence will have poor communication ability; it will lead to more problems at job which finally lead to stress. It was found in the present study that high EQ people tend to have low stress and on the other hand low EQ people tend to have more stress. Low EQ person cannot handle his/her emotion well which will create problems at job. High level EQ help the people to perform better and deal with environment effectively. It can be interpreted from the present study that emotional intelligence is an important factor to perform better at managerial level. High level emotional intelligence will lead to better performance and less stress level. High EQ is associated with general happiness. People with high EQ can recognize negative feeling and source of it, in turn can take appropriate action to deal with it. It can be concluded that emotional intelligence has important influence on occupational stress among employees at managerial level.

Conclusion

The present study provided a better understanding between emotional intelligence and occupational stress among engineers at managerial level in public sector organization. The findings showed that emotional intelligence influence occupational stress level among employee at managerial level.

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